

Original Research

**TOCOPHEROLS AND TOCOTRIENOLS IN
PALM OIL AND PALM KERNEL OIL**Ubiji, Chioma Ernest¹ and Eze, Sunday Onyekwere²¹ & ² Department of Pure and Industrial Chemistry, Abia State University,
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Ernest*****Related declarations are provided in the final section of this article.***Abstract**

About 80% of the palm oil and palm kernel oil and their fractions produced globally are used for edible purposes. The unique solid content profile of palm oil, and its excellent oxidative stability, high nutritional value and competitive price makes palm oil as one of the most utilized oils by food manufacturers. Palm Kernel oil which is derived from the flesh of the oil palm fruits' kernel is high in lauric acid and has a sharp melting, a character suitable for use in confectionery fats. Fractionation of palm oil into palm stearin, palm olein and Palm kernel oil into palm kernel stearin and palm kernel olein further enhances the usage of palm oil and Palm kernel oil in foods. Also, due to their high content of oleic acid and natural antioxidant (vitamin E) have excellent oxidative stability, hence, are a superior cooking and frying oil. Therefore, palm oil and palm kernel oil were extensively discussed as a major source of tocopherol and tocotrienols which are related compounds and also have vitamin E activity, their chemistry and metabolism were discussed as well. Palm oil and palm kernel history, compositions, processing, refining, uses, nutrition and health, producing countries, social and environmental impacts as well as markets were equally discussed in details with some recommendations at the end.

Keywords: Palm oil and palm kernel oil, tocopherol and tocotrienols, uses and environmental impacts.

1.0 Introduction

Palm oil is derived from the mesocarp of oil palm fruits, and has a balanced unsaturated (mainly oleic) and saturated (mainly palmitic) fatty acids. Palm oil is an edible vegetable oil derived from the mesocarp (reddish pulp) of the fruit of the oil palms, primarily the African oil palm *Elaeis guineensis*, and to a lesser extent from the American oil palm *Elaeis oleifera* and the maripa palm *Attalea maripa* (USDA, 2016). Palm Oil is an economically important and versatile vegetable

oil used as a raw material for both food and non-food products, and is the most widely used vegetable oil in the world (Zion Market Research, 2017). It has been used in a variety of food applications and preparation for thousands of years. About 80% of Palm Oil products are used for edible application (Basiron, 2007). Palm oil share in food use has grown to 32.5% in 2013 and will exceed 34% in the near future (Basiron, 2015). Not only because of its competitive price, the distinctive quality of Palm oil such as its natural excellent oxidative stability, unique solid content profile, high nutritional value, free of *trans* fatty acids and cholesterols, antioxidant properties and non-genetically modified makes it one of the most utilized oils by food manufacturers (Choo, 2013). Palm oil has an excellent oxidative stability as it is high in monounsaturated fatty acid (Oleic acid) and vitamin E, and low in polyunsaturated fatty acid. Hence, food products produced or processed using palm oil have a relatively long shelf-life with a low degree of rancidity. This is so, owing to its semi-solid in nature, palm oil does not require hydrogenation, a process to increase the saturated fatty acid content of liquid oil that produces *trans* fatty acids, prior to be used in food formulations. This is particularly important to food industry following the requirement of *trans* fatty acids labelling by the United States Food and Drug Administration in 2003, according to Tarrago-Trani *et al.*, (2006). There is an increasing concern on the presence of *trans* fatty acids in hydrogenated products, due to its bad adverse effect on cardiovascular health. Thus, Palm oil is a good alternative to replace the use of the animal fats in meat products such as sausages and meat patties (O'Brien, 2009).

1.1 Palm kernel oil

Palm kernel oil is an edible plant oil derived from the kernel of the oil palm *Elaeis guineensis* (Poku, 2002). Palm kernel oil (PKO) is obtained from the kernel of the oil palm fruits. Its composition and properties differ significantly from palm oil. Palm kernel oil is high in lauric acid and has a sharp melting profile; thus, it is suitable for confectioneries and other specialty fats. It should not be confused with the other two edible oils derived from palm fruits: palm oil, extracted from the pulp of the oil palm fruit, and coconut oil, extracted from the kernel of the coconut. Palm kernel oil, palm oil, and coconut oil are three of the few highly saturated vegetable fats; these oils give the name to the 16-carbon saturated fatty acid palmitic acid that they contain. Palm kernel oil, which is semi-solid at room temperature, is more saturated than palm oil and comparable to coconut oil. Historically, Oil from the African oil palm *Elaeis guineensis* has long been recognized in West African countries. European merchants trading with West Africa occasionally purchased palm oil for use in Europe, but palm kernel oil remained rare outside West Africa (Aghalino, 2000).

1.3 Tocopherols and Tocotrienols

Both tocopherols and tocotrienols are related compounds and also have vitamin E activity. Therefore, all of these various derivatives with vitamin activity may correctly be generally referred to as "vitamin E". Vitamin E is a group of eight fat soluble compounds that include four tocopherols and four tocotrienols (Traber and Bruno, 2020; M.I.C. 2015). Vitamin E exists in eight different forms, four tocopherols and four tocotrienols. All feature a chromane ring, with a hydroxyl group that can donate a hydrogen atom to reduce free radicals and a hydrophobic side chain that allows for penetration into biological membranes. Both the tocopherols and tocotrienols occur in α (alpha), β (beta), γ (gamma), and δ (delta) forms, determined by the number and position of methyl groups on the chromanol ring. The tocotrienols have the same methyl structure at the ring and the same Greek letter-methyl-notation, but differ from the analogous tocopherols by the presence of three double bonds in the hydrophobic side chain (FAO/WHO, 2013). The unsaturation of the tails gives tocotrienols only a single stereoisomeric carbon (and thus two possible isomers per structural formula, one of which occurs naturally), whereas tocopherols have three centers (and eight possible stereoisomers per structural formula, again, only one of which occurs naturally). Each form has a different biological activity (FAO/WHO, 2013). In general, the unnatural l-isomers of tocotrienols lack almost all vitamin activity, and half of the possible 8 isomers of the tocopherols (those with 2S chirality at the ring-tail junction) also lack vitamin activity. Of the stereoisomers that retain activity, increasing methylation, especially full methylation to the alpha-form, increases vitamin activity. In tocopherols, this is due to the preference of the tocopherol binding protein for the alpha-tocopherol form of the vitamin. Tocopherols and tocotrienols are fat-soluble antioxidants but also seem to have many other functions in the body. Vitamin E deficiency, which is rare and usually due to an underlying problem with digesting dietary fat rather than from a diet low in vitamin E,^[3] can cause nerve problems (U.S.N.I.H, 2019). Vitamin E is a fat-soluble antioxidant protecting cell membranes from reactive oxygen species (U.S. N. I.H, 2019). Globally, government organizations recommend adults consume in the range of 7 to 15 mg per day. As of 2016, consumption was below recommendations according to a worldwide summary of more than one hundred studies that reported a median dietary intake of 6.2 mg per day for alpha-tocopherol (Péter *et al*, 2015). Research with alpha-tocopherol as a dietary supplement, with daily amounts as high as 2000 mg per day, has had mixed results. Population studies suggested that people who consumed foods with more vitamin E, or who chose on their own to consume a vitamin E dietary supplement, had lower incidence of cardiovascular diseases, cancer, dementia, and other diseases, but placebo-controlled clinical trials could not always replicate these findings (M.I.C. 2015). As of 2017, vitamin E continues to be a topic of active clinical research (Galli *et al*,

2017). There is no clinical evidence that use of vitamin E skincare products are effective (Sidgwick *et al*, 2015). Both natural and synthetic tocopherols are subject to oxidation, and so in dietary supplements are esterified, creating tocopheryl acetate for stability purposes (M.I.C. 2015). Of the many different forms of vitamin E, gamma-tocopherol (γ -tocopherol) is the most common form found in the North American diet, but alpha-tocopherol (α -tocopherol) is the most biologically active (M.I.C. 2015). Palm oil is a source of tocotrienols. Vitamin E was discovered in 1922, isolated in 1935 and first synthesized in 1938. Because the vitamin activity was first identified as essential for fertilized eggs to result in live births (in rats), it was given the name "tocopherol" from Greek words meaning *birth* and *to bear* or *carry*. Alpha-tocopherol, either naturally extracted from plant oils or, most commonly, as the synthetic tocopheryl acetate, is sold as a popular dietary supplement, either by itself or incorporated into a multivitamin product, and in oils or lotions for use on skin (M.I.C. 2015; Sidgwick *et al*, 2015).

1.4 Chemistry of Tocopherols and Tocotrienols

1.4.1 Tocopherols

General chemical structure of tocopherols (Manolescu *et al*, 2008).

RRR alpha-tocopherol; chiral points are where the three dashed lines connect to the side chain

The nutritional content of vitamin E is defined by equivalency to 100% RRR-configuration α -tocopherol activity (Manolescu *et al*, 2008). The molecules that contribute α -tocopherol activity

are four tocopherols and four tocotrienols, within each group of four identified by the prefixes alpha- (α -), beta- (β -), gamma- (γ -), and delta- (δ -). For alpha(α)-tocopherol each of the three "R" sites has a methyl group (CH₃) attached. For beta(β)-tocopherol: R₁ = methyl group, R₂ = H, R₃ = methyl group. For gamma(γ)-tocopherol: R₁ = H, R₂ = methyl group, R₃ = methyl group. For delta(δ)-tocopherol: R₁ = H, R₂ = H, R₃ = methyl group. The same configurations exist for the tocotrienols, except that the hydrophobic side chain has three carbon-carbon double bonds whereas the tocopherols have a saturated side chain (Manolescu *et al*, 2008).

Tocopherols function by donating H atoms to radicals (X) (Lide, 2006).

Tocopherols are radical scavengers, delivering H atom to quench free radicals. At 323 kJ/mol, the O-H bond in tocopherols is approximately 10% weaker than in most other phenols (Lide, 2006). This weak bond allows the vitamin to donate a hydrogen atom to the peroxy radical and other free radicals, minimizing their damaging effect. The thus generated tocopheryl radical is relatively unreactive, but reverts to tocopherol by a redox reaction with a hydrogen donor such as vitamin C (Traber and Stevens, 2011). As they are fat-soluble, tocopherols are incorporated into cell membranes, which are protected from oxidative damage.

1.4.2 Tocotrienols

General chemical structure of tocotrienols.

The four tocotrienols (alpha, beta, gamma, delta) are similar in structure to the four tocopherols, with the main difference being that the former have hydrophobic side chains with three carbon-carbon double bonds, whereas the tocopherols have saturated side chains. For *alpha*(α)-tocotrienol each of the three "R" sites has a methyl group (CH₃) attached. For *beta*(β)-tocotrienol: R₁ = methyl

group, R2 = H, R3 = methyl group. For *gamma*(γ)-tocotrienol: R1 = H, R2 = methyl group, R3 = methyl group. For *delta*(δ)-tocotrienol: R1 = H, R2 = H, R3 = methyl group. Palm oil is a good source of alpha and gamma tocotrienols (*Shahidi and de Camargo, 2016*).

Tocotrienols have only a single chiral center, which exists at the 2' chromanol ring carbon, at the point where the isoprenoid tail joins the ring. The other two corresponding centers in the phytyl tail of the corresponding tocopherols do not exist as chiral centers for tocotrienols due to unsaturation (C-C double bonds) at these sites. Tocotrienols extracted from plants are always dextrorotatory stereoisomers, signified as d-tocotrienols. In theory, levorotatory forms of tocotrienols (l-tocotrienols) could exist as well, which would have a 2S rather than 2R configuration at the molecules' single chiral center, but unlike synthetic dl-alpha-tocopherol, the marketed tocotrienol dietary supplements are all d-tocotrienol extracts from palm or annatto oils. Preliminary clinical trials on dietary supplement tocotrienols indicate potential for anti-disease activity (*Meganathan, 2016*).

1.5 Metabolism Tocopherols and Tocotrienols

Tocotrienols and tocopherols, the latter including the stereoisomers of synthetic alpha-tocopherol, are absorbed from the intestinal lumen, incorporated into chylomicrons, and secreted into the portal vein, leading to the liver. Absorption efficiency is estimated at 51% to 86% and that applies to all of the vitamin E family – there is no discrimination among the vitamin E vitamers during absorption. Unabsorbed vitamin E is excreted via feces. Additionally, vitamin E is excreted by the liver via bile into the intestinal lumen, where it will either be reabsorbed or excreted via feces, and all of the vitamin E vitamers are metabolized and then excreted via urine (*Manolescu et al, 2008*).

Upon reaching the liver, RRR-alpha-tocopherol is preferentially taken up by alpha-tocopherol transfer protein (α -TTP). All other forms are degraded to 2'-carboxethyl-6-hydroxychromane (CEHC), a process that involves truncating the phytic tail of the molecule, then either sulfated or glycuronidated. This renders the molecules water-soluble and leads to excretion via urine. Alpha-tocopherol is also degraded by the same process, to 2, 5, 7, 8-tetramethyl-2-(2'-carboxyethyl)-6-hydroxychromane (α -CEHC), but more slowly because it is partially protected by α -TTP. Large intakes of α -tocopherol result in increased urinary α -CEHC, so this appears to be a means of disposing of excess vitamin E (*Manolescu et al, 2008*).

Alpha-tocopherol transfer protein is coded by the TTPA gene on chromosome 8. The binding site for RRR- α -tocopherol is a hydrophobic pocket with a lower affinity for beta-, gamma-, or delta-tocopherols, or for the stereoisomers with an S configuration at the chiral 2 sites. Tocotrienols are also a poor fit because the double bonds in the phytic tail create a rigid configuration that is a

mismatch with the α -TTP pocket ((Manolescu *et al*, 2008). A rare genetic defect of the TTPA gene results in people exhibiting a progressive neurodegenerative disorder known as ataxia with vitamin E deficiency (AVED) despite consuming normal amounts of vitamin E. Large amounts of α -tocopherol as a dietary supplement are needed to compensate for the lack of α -TTP. The role of α -TTP is to move α -tocopherol to the plasma membrane of hepatocytes (liver cells), where it can be incorporated into newly created very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL) molecules. These convey α -tocopherol to cells in the rest of the body. As an example of a result of the preferential treatment, the US diet delivers approximately 70 mg/d of γ -tocopherol and plasma concentrations are on the order of 2–5 μ mol/L; meanwhile, dietary α -tocopherol is about 7 mg/d but plasma concentrations are in the range of 11–37 μ mol/L (Manolescu *et al*, 2008).

2.1 History

Human beings used oil palms as far back as 5,000 years. In the late 1800s, archaeologists discovered a substance that they concluded was originally palm oil in a tomb at Abydos dating back to 3,000 BC (Kenneth *et al*, 2000). It is believed that traders brought oil palm to Egypt.

According to African Study Monographs in 2013, palm oil from *Elaeis guineensis* has long been recognized in West and Central African countries, and is widely used as a cooking oil. European merchants trading with West Africa occasionally purchased palm oil for use as a cooking oil in Europe. The use of palm oil in food and beauty products has attracted the concern of environmental groups; the high oil yield of the trees has encouraged wider cultivation, leading to the clearing of forests in parts of Indonesia and Malaysia to make space for oil-palm monoculture (sustainablepalmoil.org, 2016). This has resulted in significant acreage losses of the natural habitat of the three surviving species of orangutan. One species in particular, the Sumatran orangutan, has been listed as critically endangered (IUCN, 2016; Gilbert, 2012).

Palm oil became a highly sought-after commodity by British traders for use as an industrial lubricant for machinery during Britain's Industrial Revolution (African Study Monographs, 2013). Palm oil formed the basis of soap products, such as Lever Brothers' (now Unilever) "Sunlight" soap, and the American Palmolive brand (Bellis, 1864).

By around 1870, palm oil constituted the primary export of some West African countries, although this was overtaken by cocoa in the 1880s with the introduction of colonial European cocoa plantations.

2.3 Composition of Palm Oil and Palm Kernel Oil

Left, reddish palm oil made from the pulp of oil palm fruit. Right, clear palm kernel oil made from the kernels according to Oi-Ming *et al*, 2015.

2.3.1 Fatty Acids

Palm oil, like all fats, is composed of fatty acids, esterified with glycerol. Palm oil has an especially high concentration of saturated fat, specifically the 16-carbon saturated fatty acid, palmitic acid, to which it gives its name. Monounsaturated oleic acid is also a major constituent of palm oil. Unrefined palm oil is a significant source of tocotrienol, part of the vitamin E family (Ahsan *et al*, 2015; Akoh *et al*, 2015).

Fatty acid content of palm oil (present as triglyceride esters)

Type of fatty acid	Fraction
<u>Myristic</u> saturated C ₁₄	1.0%
<u>Palmitic</u> saturated C ₁₆	43.5%
<u>Stearic</u> saturated C ₁₈	4.3%
<u>Oleic</u> monounsaturated C ₁₈ :1	36.6%
<u>Linoleic</u> polyunsaturated C ₁₈ :2	9.1%
Other/unknown	5.5%

The approximate concentration of esterified fatty acids in palm oil is (USDA, 2014).

2.3.2 Carotenes

Red palm oil is rich in carotenes, such as alpha-carotene, beta-carotene and lycopene, which give it a characteristic dark red color (Akoh *et al*, 2015; Choo *et al*, 2016). However, palm oil that has been refined, bleached and deodorized from crude palm oil (called "RBD palm oil") does not contain carotenes (Nagendran *et al*, 2000).

3.0 Processing of Palm oil and Palm Kernel Oil

Oil palm fruits on the tree

An oil palm stem, with some of its fruits picked

Palm oil is naturally reddish in color because of a high beta-carotene content. It is not to be confused with palm kernel oil derived from the kernel of the same fruit (Poku, 2002) or coconut oil derived from the kernel of the coconut palm (*Cocos nucifera*). The differences are in color (raw palm kernel oil lacks carotenoids and is not red), and in saturated fat content: palm mesocarp oil is 49% saturated, while palm kernel oil and coconut oil are 81% and 86% saturated fats, respectively. However, crude red palm oil that has been refined, bleached and deodorized, a common commodity called RBD (refined, bleached, and deodorized) palm oil, does not contain carotenoids (Nagendran *et al*, 2000). Many industrial food applications of palm oil use fractionated components of palm oil (often listed as "modified palm oil") whose saturation levels can reach 90%;(Gibon, 2012) these "modified" palm oils can become highly saturated, but are not necessarily hydrogenated. The oil palm produces bunches containing many fruits with the fleshy mesocarp enclosing a kernel that is covered by a very hard shell. The FAO considers palm oil (coming from the pulp) and palm kernels to be primary products. The oil extraction rate from a bunch varies from 17 to 27% for palm oil, and from 4 to 10% for palm kernels (FAO, 2018). Along with coconut oil, palm oil is one of the few highly saturated vegetable fats and is semisolid at room temperature (Behrman and Gopalan, 2005). Palm oil is a common cooking ingredient in the tropical belt of Africa, Southeast Asia and parts of Brazil. Its use in the commercial food industry in other parts of the world is widespread because of its lower cost and the high oxidative stability (saturation) of the refined product when used for frying (Matthäus, 2007). One source reported that humans consumed an average 17 pounds (7.7 kg) of palm oil per person in 2015(Raghu, 2017). Many processed foods either contain palm oil or various ingredients made from it.

3.1 Refining of Palm oil and Palm Kernel Oil

After milling, various palm oil products are made using refining processes. First is fractionation, with crystallization and separation processes to obtain solid (palm stearin), and liquid (olein) fractions. Then melting and degumming removes impurities. Then the oil is filtered and bleached. Physical refining removes smells and coloration to produce "refined, bleached and deodorized palm oil" (RBDPO) and free fatty acids, which are used in the manufacture of soaps, washing powder and other products. RBDPO is the basic palm oil product sold on the world's commodity markets. Many companies fractionate it further to produce palm oil for cooking oil, or process it into other products.

3.2 Uses of Palm oil and Palm Kernel Oil

3.2.1 Red palm oil

Since the mid-1990s, **red palm oil** has been cold-pressed from the fruit of the oil palm and bottled for use as a cooking oil, in addition to other uses such as being blended into mayonnaise and vegetable oil (Nagendran *et al*, 2000). Oil produced from palm fruit is called *red palm oil* or just *palm oil*. It is around 50% saturated fat—considerably less than palm kernel oil—and 40% unsaturated fat and 10% polyunsaturated fat. In its unprocessed state, red palm oil has an intense deep red color because of its abundant carotene content. Like palm kernel oil, red palm oil contains around 50% medium chain fatty acids, but it also contains the following nutrients:

- Carotenoids, such as alpha-carotene, beta-carotene, and lycopene
- Sterols
- Vitamin E

3.2.2 White palm oil

White palm oil is the result of processing and refining. When refined, the palm oil loses its deep red color. It is extensively used in food manufacture and can be found in a variety of processed foods including peanut butter and chips. It is often labeled as palm shortening and is used as a replacement ingredient for hydrogenated fats in a variety of baked and fried products.

3.2.3 Use in food

The highly saturated nature of palm oil renders it solid at room temperature in temperate regions, making it a cheap substitute for butter or hydrogenated vegetable oils in uses where solid fat is desirable, such as the making of pastry dough and baked goods. The health concerns related to trans fats in hydrogenated vegetable oils may have contributed to the increasing use of palm oil in

the food industry. Palm oil is also used in animal feed. In March 2017, a documentary made by Deutsche Welle revealed that palm oil is used to make milk substitutes to feed calves in dairies in the German alps. These milk substitutes contain 30% milk powder and the remainder of raw protein made from skimmed milk powder, whey powder, and vegetable fats, mostly coconut oil and palm oil (Deutsche, 2017).

3.2.4 Biomass and biofuels

Palm oil is used to produce both methyl ester and hydro deoxygenated biodiesel (Rojas, 2007) Palm oil methyl ester is created through a process called transesterification. Palm oil biodiesel is often blended with other fuels to create palm oil biodiesel blends (Nahian *et al*, 2016). Palm oil biodiesel meets the European EN14214 standard for biodiesels (Rojas, 2007). Hydrodeoxygenated biodiesel is produced by direct hydrogenolysis of the fat into alkanes and propane. The world's largest palm oil biodiesel plant is the €550 million Finnish-operated Neste Oil biodiesel plant in Singapore, which opened in 2011 with a capacity of 800,000 tons per year and produces hydrodeoxygenated biodiesel from palm oil imported from Malaysia and Indonesia (Yahya, 2011; Tuck, 2011). Significant amounts of palm oil exports to Europe are converted to biodiesel (as of early 2018: Indonesia: 40%, Malaysia 30% (Hermes, 2018; Wahyudi and Trinna, 2018). In 2014, almost half of all the palm oil in Europe was burnt as car and truck fuel (Hall, 2016). As of 2018, one-half of Europe's palm oil imports were used for biodiesel (Robert and de Carbonnel, 2018). Use of palm oil as biodiesel generates three times the carbon emissions as using fossil fuel (Hans, 2018), and, for example, "biodiesel made from Indonesian palm oil makes the global carbon problem worse, not better (Abrahm, 2018)." The organic waste matter that is produced when processing oil palm, including oil palm shells and oil palm fruit bunches, can also be used to produce energy. This waste material can be converted into pellets that can be used as a biofuel (Choong, 2012). Additionally, palm oil that has been used to fry foods can be converted into methyl esters for biodiesel. The used cooking oil is chemically treated to create a biodiesel similar to petroleum diesel.

3.2.5 In wound care

Although palm oil is applied to wounds for its supposed antimicrobial effects, research does not confirm its effectiveness (Ekwenye and Ijeomah, 2008).

3.3 Nutrition and Health

Contributing significant calories as a source of fat, palm oil is a food staple in many cuisines (Bradsher, 2008). On average globally, humans consumed 7.7 kg (17 lb) of palm oil per person in 2015 (Raghu, 2017). Although the relationship of palm oil consumption to disease risk has been

previously assessed, the quality of the clinical research specifically assessing palm oil effects has been generally poor (Mancini *et al*, 2015). Consequently, research has focused on the deleterious effects of palm oil and palmitic acid consumption as sources of saturated fat content in edible oils, leading to conclusions that palm oil and saturated fats should be replaced with polyunsaturated fats in the diet(Sacks *et al*, 2017; Mozaffarian and Clarke, 2009). A 2015 meta-analysis and 2017 advisory from the American Heart Association indicated that palm oil is among foods supplying dietary saturated fat which increases blood levels of LDL cholesterol and increased risk of cardiovascular diseases, leading to recommendations for reduced use or elimination of dietary palm oil in favor of consuming hydrogenated vegetable oils(Sun *et al*, 2015; American Heart Association, 2019).

Glycidyl fatty acid esters (GE), 3-MCPD and 2-MCPD, are found especially in palm oils and palm fats because of their refining at high temperatures (approx. 200 °C (392 °F))(European Food Safety Authority, 2016). Since glycidol, the parent compound of GE, is considered genotoxic and carcinogenic, the EFSA didn't set a safe level for GE. According to the chair of the CONTAM (EFSA's expert Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain), "The exposure to GE of babies consuming solely infant formula is a particular concern as this is up to ten times what would be considered of low concern for public health"(European Food Safety Authority, 2016). The EFSA's tolerable daily intake (TDI) of 3-MCPD and its fatty acid esters was set to 0.8 micrograms per kilogram of body weight per day ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}/\text{day}$) in 2016 and increased to 2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}/\text{day}$ in 2017, based on evidence linking this substance to organ damage in animal tests and on possible adverse effects on the kidney and on male fertility. According to the EFSA, there is not enough data to set a safe level for 2-MCPD (*European Food Safety Authority*, 2016).

3.4 Palmitic Acid

Excessive intake of palmitic acid, which makes up 44% of palm oil, increases blood levels of low-density lipoprotein (LDL) and total cholesterol, and so increases risk of cardiovascular diseases(Sacks *et al*, 2017; Mozaffarian and Clarke, 2009). Other reviews, the World Health Organization, and the US National Heart, Lung and Blood Institute have encouraged consumers to limit the consumption of palm oil, palmitic acid and foods high in saturated fat (European Food Safety Authority, 2020).

4.0 Production of Palm oil and Palm Kernel Oil

In 2016, the global production of palm oil was estimated at 62.6 million tons, 2.7 million tons more than in 2015. The palm oil production value was estimated at \$US39.3 billion in 2016, an increase of \$US2.4 billion (or +7%) against the production figure recorded in the previous year (Global

Palm Oil Market Overview, 2018). Between 1962 and 1982 global exports of palm oil increased from around half a million to 2.4 million tons annually and in 2008 world production of palm oil and palm kernel oil amounted to 48 million tons. According to FAO forecasts by 2020 the global demand for palm oil will double, and triple by 2050.

4.1.1 Indonesia

Indonesia is the world's largest producer of palm oil, surpassing Malaysia in 2006, producing more than 20.9 million tons, a number that has since risen to over 34.5 million tons (2016 output). Indonesia expects to double production by the end of 2030 (Gilbert, 2012). By 2019, this number was 51.8 million tons. At the end of 2010, 60% of the output was exported in the form of crude palm oil. FAO data shows production increased by over 400% between 1994 and 2004, to over 8.7 million metric tons.

4.1.2 Malaysia

Malaysia is the world's second largest producer of palm oil. In 1992, in response to concerns about deforestation, the Government of Malaysia pledged to limit the expansion of palm oil plantations by retaining a minimum of half the nation's land as forest cover (Morales, 2010; Scott-Thomas, 2012). In 2012, produced 18.8 million tons of crude palm oil on roughly 5,000,000 hectares (19,000 sq mi) of land (Pakiam, 2013). Though Indonesia produces more palm oil, Malaysia is the world's largest exporter of palm oil having exported 18 million tons of palm oil products in 2011. India, China, Pakistan, the European Union and the United States are the primary importers of Malaysian palm oil products. In 2016, palm oil prices jumped to a four-year high days after Trump's election victory in the US.

4.1.3 Nigeria

As of 2018, Nigeria was the third-largest producer, with approximately 2.3 million hectares (5.7 million acres) under cultivation. Until 1934, Nigeria had been the world's largest producer. Both small- and large-scale producers participated in the industry (Ayodele, 2010).

4.1.4 Thailand

Thailand is the world's third largest producer of crude palm oil, producing approximately two million tons per year, or 1.2% of global output. Nearly all of Thai production is consumed locally. Almost 85% of palm plantations and extraction mills are in south Thailand. At year-end 2016, 4.7 to 5.8 million rai (750,000 to 930,000 hectares) were planted in oil palms, employing 300,000 farmers, mostly on small landholdings of 20 rai (3.2 ha). ASEAN as a region accounts for 52.5 million tons of palm oil production, about 85% of the world total and more than 90% of global exports.

Indonesia accounts for 52% of world exports. Malaysian exports total 38%. The biggest consumers of palm oil are India, the European Union, and China, with the three consuming nearly 50% of world exports. Thailand's Department of Internal Trade (DIT) usually sets the price of crude palm oil and refined palm oil. Thai farmers have a relatively low yield compared to those in Malaysia and Indonesia. Thai palm oil crops yield 4–17% oil compared to around 20% in competing countries. In addition, Indonesian and Malaysian oil palm plantations are 10 times the size of Thai plantations (Arunmas and Wipatayotin, 2018).

4.1.5 Colombia

In 2018, total palm oil production in Colombia reached 1.6 million tons, representing some 8% of national agricultural GDP and benefiting mainly smallholders (65% of Colombia's palm oil sector) (Inga *et al*, 2019). According to a study from the Environmental, Science and Policy, Colombia has the potential to produce sustainable palm oil without causing deforestation (Carmenza *etal*, 2013). In addition, palm oil and other crops provide a productive alternative for illegal crops, like coca (David and Carlos, 2019).

4.1.6 Ecuador

Ecuador aims to help palm oil producers switch to sustainable methods and achieve RSPO certification under initiatives to develop greener industries.

4.1.7 Benin

Palm is native to the wetlands of western Africa, and south Benin already hosts many palm plantations. Its 'Agricultural Revival Programme' has identified many thousands of hectares of land as suitable for new oil palm export plantations. In spite of the economic benefits, Non-governmental organisations (NGOs), such as Nature Tropicale, claim biofuels will compete with domestic food production in some existing prime agricultural sites. Other areas comprise peat land, whose drainage would have a deleterious environmental impact. They are also concerned genetically modified plants will be introduced into the region, jeopardizing the current premium paid for their non-GM crops. According to recent article by National Geographic, most palm oil in Benin is still produced by women for domestic use. The FAO additionally states that peasants in Benin practice agroecology. They harvest palm fruit from small farms and the palm oil is mostly used for local consumption.

4.1.8 Cameroon

Cameroon had a production project underway initiated by Herakles Farms in the US. However, the project was halted under the pressure of civil society organizations in Cameroon. Before the project

was halted, Herakles left the Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil early in negotiations. The project has been controversial due to opposition from villagers and the location of the project in a sensitive region for biodiversity.

4.1.9 Kenya

Kenya's domestic production of edible oils covers about a third of its annual demand, estimated at around 380,000 tons. The rest is imported at a cost of around US\$140 million a year, making edible oil the country's second most important import after petroleum. Since 1993 a new hybrid variety of cold-tolerant, high-yielding oil palm has been promoted by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations in western Kenya. As well as alleviating the country's deficit of edible oils while providing an important cash crop, it is claimed to have environmental benefits in the region, because it does not compete against food crops or native vegetation and it provides stabilization for the soil (UN FAO, 2003).

4.1.10 Ghana

Ghana has a lot of palm nut species, which may become an important contributor to the agriculture of the region. Although Ghana has multiple palm species, ranging from local palm nuts to other species locally called Agric, it was only marketed locally and to neighboring countries. Production is now expanding as major investment funds are purchasing plantations, because Ghana is considered a major growth area for palm oil.

4.2 Social and Environmental Impacts

4.2.1 Social

The palm oil industry has had both positive and negative impacts on workers, indigenous peoples and residents of palm oil-producing communities. Palm oil production provides employment opportunities, and has been shown to improve infrastructure, social services and reduce poverty (Budidarsono *et al*, 2013). However, in some cases, oil palm plantations have developed lands without consultation or compensation of the indigenous people inhabiting the land, resulting in social conflict (Colchester *et al*, 2012). The use of illegal immigrants in Malaysia has also raised concerns about working conditions within the palm oil industry (BBC News, 2013).

Some social initiatives use palm oil cultivation as part of poverty alleviation strategies. Examples include the UN Food and Agriculture Organization's hybrid oil palm project in Western Kenya, which improves incomes and diets of local populations, and Malaysia's Federal Land Development Authority and Federal Land Consolidation and Rehabilitation Authority, which both support rural development (Ibrahim, 2012).

4.2.2 Food versus fuel

The use of palm oil in the production of biodiesel has led to concerns that the need for fuel is being placed ahead of the need for food, leading to malnutrition in developing nations. This is known as the food versus fuel debate. According to a 2008 report published in the Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, palm oil was determined to be a sustainable source of both food and biofuel, and the production of palm oil biodiesel does not pose a threat to edible palm oil supplies. According to a 2009 study published in the Environmental Science and Policy journal, palm oil biodiesel might increase the demand for palm oil in the future, resulting in the expansion of palm oil production, and therefore an increased supply of food (Corley, 2009).

4.2.3 Human rights

One report indicated numerous allegations of human rights violations in the production of palm oil in Indonesia and Malaysia, including exposure to hazardous pesticides, child labor, and rape and sexual abuse, and unsafe carrying loads. These incidents may receive no response by the company or police, or are left unreported because victims fear retaliation from their abuser. The chemicals used in the pesticides, such as paraquat and glyphosate, have been banned in other countries because they may be pathogens in diseases, such as Parkinson's disease and cancer (Margie and Robin, 2020).

4.3 Environmental effects

While only 5% of the world's vegetable oil farmland is used for palm plantations, palm cultivation produces 38% of the world's total vegetable oil supply. In terms of oil yield, a palm plantation is 10 times more productive than soybean, sunflower or rapeseed cultivation because the palm fruit and kernel both provide usable oil (Spinks, 2014). Palm oil is the most sustainable vegetable oil in terms of yield, requiring one-ninth of land used by other vegetable oil crops. In the future, laboratory-grown microbes might achieve higher yields per unit of land at comparable prices (Paddison, 2017). However palm oil cultivation has been criticized for its impact on the natural environment, including deforestation, loss of natural habitats and greenhouse gas emissions (Foster, 2012; Yui and Yeh, 2013) which have threatened critically endangered species, such as the orangutan and Sumatran tiger.

Environmental groups such as Greenpeace and Friends of the Earth oppose the use of palm oil biofuels, claiming that the deforestation caused by oil palm plantations is more damaging for the climate than the benefits gained by switching to biofuel and using the palms as carbon sinks (Fargione *et al*, 2008).

A 2018 study by the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) concluded that palm oil is "here to stay" due to its higher productivity compared with many other vegetable oils. The IUCN maintains that replacing palm oil with other vegetable oils would necessitate greater amounts of agricultural land, negatively affecting biodiversity (Meijaard, 2018). The IUCN advocates better practices in the palm oil industry, including the prevention of plantations from expanding into forested regions and creating a demand for certified and sustainable palm oil products (Meijaard, 2018).

In 2019 the Rainforest Action Network surveyed eight global brands involved in palm oil extraction in the Leuser Ecosystem, and said that none was performing adequately in avoiding "conflict palm oil". Many of the companies told the Guardian they were working to improve their performance. A WWF scorecard rated only 15 out of 173 companies as performing well.

In 2020 a study by Chain Reaction Research concluded that NDPE (No Deforestation, No Peat, No Exploitation) policies cover 83% of palm oil refineries. NDPE policies are according to the Chain Reaction Research the most effective private mechanism to cut the direct link with deforestation, due to the economic leverage refineries have over palm oil growers (Chain Reaction Research, 2020).

4.4 Markets

According to the Hamburg-based Oil World trade journal in 2020, in 2008 global production of oils and fats stood at 160 million tons. Palm oil and palm kernel oil were jointly the largest contributor, accounting for 48 million tons, or 30% of the total output. Soybean oil came in second with 37 million tons (23%). About 38% of the oils and fats produced in the world were shipped across oceans. Of the 60 million tons of oils and fats exported around the world, palm oil and palm kernel oil made up close to 60%; Malaysia, with 45% of the market share, dominated the palm oil trade.

4.4.1 Food Label Regulations

Previously, palm oil could be listed as "vegetable fat" or "vegetable oil" on food labels in the European Union (EU). From December 2014, food packaging in the EU is no longer allowed to use the generic terms "vegetable fat" or "vegetable oil" in the ingredients list. Food producers are required to list the specific type of vegetable fat used, including palm oil. Vegetable oils and fats can be grouped together in the ingredients list under the term "vegetable oils" or "vegetable fats" but this must be followed by the type of vegetable origin (e.g., palm, sunflower, or rapeseed) and the phrase "in varying proportions"(USDA, 2012).

4.4.2 Supply chain institutions

4.4.2.1 Consumer Goods Forum

In 2010 the Consumer Goods Forum passed a resolution that its members would reduce deforestation through their palm oil supply to net zero by 2020.

4.5 Conclusion

Palm oil is an edible vegetable oil derived from the mesocarp (reddish pulp) of the fruit of the oil palms, primarily the African oil palm *Elaeis guineensis*, and to a lesser extent from the American oil palm *Elaeis oleifera* and the maripa palm *Attalea maripa*. Palm kernel oil is also an edible plant oil derived from the kernel of the oil palm *Elaeis guineensis*. Its composition and properties differ significantly from palm oil. Palm kernel oil is high in lauric acid and has a sharp melting profile; thus, it is suitable for confectioneries and other specialty fats.

Palm oil and Palm kernel oil and their fractions are very versatile. They can be used in many food applications from cooking/frying oil to margarine, fat spreads, confectionery fat, animal fat replacer, health supplements, and many others. They are the major sources of tocopherols and tocotrienols which are compounds that make up vitamin E. The versatility of Palm oil, Palm kernel oil and their fractions in food applications is attributable to their availability, competitive price (in the case of Palm oil and its fractions), their distinctive quality such as their natural excellent oxidative stability (in the case of Palm oil and Palm kernel oil), unique solid content profile, high nutritional value (free of *trans* fatty acids and cholesterol, and high in micronutrients), antioxidant properties and naturalness (non-genetically modified organism, (non-GMO).

The palm oil industry has had both positive and negative impacts on workers, indigenous peoples and residents of palm oil-producing communities. Palm oil production provides employment opportunities, and has been shown to improve infrastructure, social services and reduce poverty. However, in some cases, oil palm plantations have developed lands without consultation or compensation of the indigenous people inhabiting the land, resulting in social conflict. The use of illegal immigrants in some countries such as: Malaysia has also raised concerns about working conditions within the palm oil industry.

A report has it that palm oil could be a sustainable source of both food and biofuel, and the production of palm oil biodiesel does not pose a threat to edible palm oil supplies. However palm oil cultivation has been criticized for its impact on the natural environment, including deforestation, loss of natural habitats and greenhouse gas emissions which have threatened critically endangered species, such as the orangutan and Sumatran tiger. Environmental

groups such as Greenpeace and Friends of the Earth oppose the use of palm oil biofuels, claiming that the deforestation caused by oil palm plantations is more damaging for the climate than the benefits gained by switching to biofuel and using the palms as carbon sinks.

Both tocopherols and tocotrienols are related compounds and also have vitamin E activity, and their various derivatives with vitamin activity could be referred to as "vitamin E". Vitamin E is a group of eight fat soluble compounds that include four tocopherols and four tocotrienols. All feature a chromane ring, with a hydroxyl group that can donate a hydrogen atom to reduce free radicals and a hydrophobic side chain that allows for penetration into biological membranes. Both the tocopherols and tocotrienols occur in α (alpha), β (beta), γ (gamma), and δ (delta) forms, determined by the number and position of methyl groups on the chromanol ring. The tocotrienols have the same methyl structure at the ring and the same Greek letter-methyl-notation, but differ from the analogous tocopherols by the presence of three double bonds in the hydrophobic side chain.

4.6 Recommendations

- There should be orientation to advocates for a better practice in the palm oil industry, including the prevention of plantations from expanding into forest regions and creating a demand for certified and sustainable palm oil products.
- The use of illegal immigrants in some countries like Malaysia which has also raised concerns about working conditions within the palm oil industry should be addressed and discourage so as to avoid conflicts.
- The use of chemicals and pesticides, such as paraquat and glyphosate, should be prohibited since there may be pathogens capable of causing diseases, such as Parkinson's disease and cancer.
- There should be strong 'No Deforestation, No Peat and No Exploitation' policies guarding palm oil refineries. Such policies will be the most effective mechanism to cut the direct link with deforestation, due to the economic leverage refineries have over palm oil growers.

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